

Oak Openings Preserve Project, Lucas County (41.58036, -83.86780)

Since construction in 2021, the Oak Openings Preserve Project’s primary known nutrient benefit has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing approximately 0.5 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. The nutrient filtration and overall wetland function of this Project was likely limited under dry climatic conditions in 2024, though several pools held 10 – 20 cm of water throughout the year. The sources of water to this Project and the effect of its sandy soils remain unclear and limit complete understanding of its impact.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 22 acres of restored wetland, consisting of 15 wetland pools that are arranged into four main flow paths. All four flow paths receive water from surface runoff, and they all drain into the same stream-seep wetland outlet that flows into a nearby stream. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which the flow paths receive surface runoff.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
22 acres	0.5 lbs	26 ± 13 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar isolated wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Assess soil texture to inform prediction of the Project’s capacity to hold water/nutrients and/or indicate connection to groundwater.
- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.